

N-Mannich Bases of 3,5-Dibromosalicylamide and 3,5-Dichlorosalicylamide: Part II.

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In continuation of our work on the α -aminoalkylation of some amide functions¹, the N-Mannich bases of 3,5-dibromosalicylamide² and 3,5-dichlorosalicylamide have been prepared, using some aliphatic and heterocyclic secondary amines. As is expected, the introduction of the halogen atoms in the benzene ring not only facilitates α -aminoalkylation but also, to some extent, favourably affects the therapeutic activity. Infra-red absorption spectra of these N-Mannich bases and other chemical evidences establish them as the carbamido derivatives. Their mode of formation and mechanism has been discussed. They also behave as Lewis-bases and could be estimated in non-aqueous media.

Bavin *et al*³ found that salicylamide is three times more potent than aspirin (acetylsalicylic acid) as an analgesic with fewer side-effects. Reichert⁴ found that salicylamide showed strong sedative effect and in higher doses also a distinct narcotic effect. The relationship between the analgesic effect and chemical structure of salicylamide derivatives was studied by Fuzimura⁵, who demonstrated that successive N-methylation increased the analgesic activity.

Kanzo *et al*⁶ tested 3,5-dichlorosalicylamide and 3,5-dibromosalicylamide along with their alkylamides for their chemotherapeutics for dermatomycoses on *Trichophyton* and *Achorion* and found them effective upto dilution of 1:32000. The fungi did not easily acquire resistance in these compounds. They also reported the bactericidal and insecticidal activity of some of these compounds. Leongway *et al*⁷ studied various congeners of salicylamide with small substituents in various positions in benzene ring or phenolic-O or amido-N and found most of them C.N.S. depressant and some even hypnotic. Ravenberg⁸ prepared morpholinoalkyl ethers of salicylamide and found that they had superior Wolf Hardy therapeutic index. Rosshart⁹ found the LD₅₀ of salicylamide and bromosalicylamide and concluded that bromosalicylamide is less toxic than salicylamide.

Most of the alkaloids and synthetic drugs possess in their molecules a basic amino-alkyl chain/reduced aza-heterocyclic system(s), which confers on them the therapeutic and chemical properties¹⁰. This principle of introducing an aminoalkyl chain has yielded good

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2. Paper presented at the 2nd. annual convention of the Indian Chemical Society, held at Allahabad in December 1964.
3. Bavin *et al.*, *J. Pharm Pharmacol.*, 1952, 14, 872.
4. B. Reichert, *Arzneimittel. Forsch.*, 1953, 3, 255.
5. Fuzimura, *Chem. Abs.*, 1953, 47, 9561.
6. Kanzo *et al.*, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1952, 72, 1039.
7. Leongway *et al.*, *J. Pharmacol. Exptl. Therap.*, 1953, 100, 450.
8. Ravenberg, *Chem. Ab.*, 1951, 35, 4445^a.
9. E. Rosshart, *J. Pharmacol.*, 1947, 89, 205.
10. Singh, G. B., *Pharmazistent*, 1966 14, 43.

dividends in drug design and drug syntheses. For the introduction of a smaller aminoalkyl chain, particularly for α -aminoalkylation an expedient and an elegant method is available in Mannich Condensation. Realising the importance of the halogen derivatives of salicylamide in medicinal chemistry, 3, 5-dibromosalicylamide¹¹ and 3,5-dichlorosalicylamide^{12,13} were prepared and submitted to α -aminoalkylation (Mannich Condensation), using formaldehyde and various secondary amines in equimolecular quantities (0.02M) under mild conditions¹.

TABLE I

N-Mannich Bases of 3, 5-dibromosalicylamide

	M.P.	Yield	Formula	Found		Mol. Wt. †	
				Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	
I. N-(Dimethylamino-methyl)BS	158-59*	81%	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂	C: 33.71% H: 3.41 N: 7.97 Br: 45.23	34.12% 3.43 7.96 45.40	351.2	352.0
II. N-(Diethylamino-methyl)BS	126-27*	99	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂	C: 37.62 H: 4.41 N: 7.32 Br: 41.85	37.91 4.24 7.37 42.04	379.4	380
III. N-(Diethanolamino-methyl)BS	133-34*	50	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₂ Br ₂	C: 35.00 H: 4.28 N: 6.60 Br: 38.70	34.97 3.91 6.80 38.78	411.3	412
IV. N-(Piperidino-methyl)BS	146-47*	58	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂	C: 39.61 H: 4.18 N: 7.00 Br: 40.33	39.81 4.11 7.15 40.76	392.2	392.1
V. N-(Morpholino-methyl)BS	166-68*	76	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂	C: 36.76 H: 3.59 N: 6.90 Br: 40.31	36.57 3.58 7.11 40.53	396.4	394.1
VI. N-(Pyrrolidino-methyl)BS	151-53*	84.5	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂	C: 37.82 H: 3.69 N: 7.50 Br: 41.95	38.12 3.73 7.41 42.27	378.1	378
VII. NN'-Bis-(3,5-dibromosalicylamidomethyl) piperazine	132-33*	99.0	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄ Br ₄	C: 34.01 H: 2.79 N: 7.9 Br: 45.19	34.32 2.88 8.0 45.67	697.0	700 (Eq. Wt. 348.5x2)
VIII. N-(Diethylamino-methyl)BS	172-73*	52.0	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂	N: 6.13 Br: 36.21	6.43 36.65	433.0	436
IX. N-(Dibenzylamino-methyl)BS	122-24*	42	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂	N: 5.23 Br: 31.21	5.54 31.70	501.6	504.2
X. N-(Dicyclohexylamino-methyl)BS.	61-62*	31	C ₂₀ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂	N: 5.53 Br: 32.40	5.73 32.73	485.3	488.2

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. BS denotes 3,5-Dibromosalicylamide. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method.

†Molecular Weight by non-aqueous titration. Bromine was estimated by Stephanow method.

11. Spilker, *Rev.*, 1889, 22, 2769.

12. Smith, *ibid.*, 1878, 11, 1225.

13. William, R. *et. al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951 73, 1500.

It may be noted that in the formation of the N-Mannich bases of salicylamide, an additional amount of hydrochloric acid (proton) is essential¹. However, when a halogen atom, Cl or Br has been introduced in the benzene ring of salicylamide, they do not require any additional proton for the formation of their N-Mannich bases. These electron attracting atoms in 3, 5-dichlorosalicylamide and 3,5-dibromosalicylamide on account of their induction effect/resonance facilitate the ionisation of these amides in the same manner as they do in the case of α -halogen substituted fatty acids or halogen substituted phenols or nitrophenols. In this way the formation of the carbonium cation R_2N-C^+ is induced without the addition of a proton, as postulated by Liebermann and Wagner¹⁴. With the introduction of Cl or Br, there is not only the ease of formation of the Mannich bases but also a considerable increase in their yield.

TABLE II

N-Mannich Bases of 3,5-dichlorosalicylamide

	M.P.	Yield	Formula	Found	Reqd.	Molecular Wt.†	
						Found	Reqd.
I. N-(Dimethylamino-methyl)ClS	157-58°	61%	$C_{10}H_{18}O_2N_2Cl_2$	N:10.34% Cl:26.51	10.64% 26.96	260.9	263.1
II. N-(Diethylamino-methyl)ClS	171-72° (d)	47	$C_{12}H_{18}O_2N_2Cl_2$	N: 9.27 Cl:24.48	9.62 24.32	287.9	291.1
III. N-(Dibutylamino-methyl) ClS	160-61	53	$C_{18}H_{24}O_2N_2Cl_2$	N: 8.13 Cl:20.26	8.06 20.42	344.5	347.2
IV. N-(Piperidinomethyl) ClS	146-47	65	$C_{13}H_{18}O_2N_2Cl_2$	N: 9.13 Cl:23.08	9.24 23.40	300.2	303
V. N-(Morpholinomethyl) ClS	117-18	69	$C_{12}H_{14}O_2N_2Cl_2$	N: 9.03 Cl:22.90	9.19 23.25	302.8	305
VI. N-(Pyrrolidinomethyl) ClS	124-25	73	$C_{12}H_{14}O_2N_2Cl_2$	N: 9.81 Cl:24.11	9.68 24.52	287.7	289
VII. NN'-Bis (3,5-dichloro-salicyl-amido-methyl)piperazine	181-82	90	$C_{20}H_{20}O_4N_4Cl_4$	N:10.36 Cl:13.30	10.73 13.58	517.8	522

*All m.p.s. are uncorrected. ClS denotes 3,5-dichlorosalicylamide. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method.

†Molecular Weight by non-aqueous titration. Bromine was estimated by Stepanow's method.

These N-Mannich bases are too weak to give a sharp end-point in aqueous media, nevertheless, like some alkaloids, they behave as Lewis-bases accepting a proton on the nitrogen atom of the aminoalkyl rest, so they have been estimated satisfactorily by titrating them with standard acetic perchloric acid.^{15,16}

14. Liebermann and Wagner, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1949, 14, 1001.

15. Vogel, A. I., 'Elementary Practical Organic Chemistry', Part III, Longmans Green & Co., London, 1958, 663.

16. Beckett, A. H. and Stenlake, J. B., 'Practical Pharmaceutical Chemistry', Asia Publishing House, Bombay, 1962, 112.

Structure of the N-Mannich Bases of the 3,5-dibromosalicylamide and 3,5-dichlorosalicylamide.

In the Mannich Condensation of these compounds, the entrant aminoalkyl group could occupy any one of the following possible positions:

(a) Like most of the alcohols¹⁷, it might replace phenolic hydrogen atom, yielding O, N-acetal.

Since all the Mannich bases of these compounds, dissolved in ethanol, turn purple on treatment with alcoholic ferric chloride solution indicating the presence of the phenolic group; so this possibility is ruled out.

(b) Since the *ortho/para* positions with respect to phenolic -OH¹⁸ are already occupied by the halogen atoms, the possibility of the entrance of the aminoalkyl moiety at these positions could be ruled out.

(c) As in the case of salicylamide¹ and other primary amides¹⁹, the aminoalkyl group could replace the amido hydrogen atom, yielding the *carboxamido derivatives*.

When N-(dimethylaminomethyl) 3,5-dibromosalicylamide (1.5 g) is refluxed with alcoholic HCl (10 ml ethanol and 10 ml HCl for 6-7 hours, it yields 3,5-dibromosalicylic acid as a residue (m.p. 215-17°, lit.²⁰ 217-19°) and the filtrate contains dimethylamine hydrochloride and ammonium chloride, which are discernible on treatment with conc. NaOH.

This indicated clearly that these N-Mannich bases are the carboxamido derivatives.

Infra red absorption spectra of these Mannich bases—In the present investigation, the I.R. absorption spectra²¹ of 3, 5-dichlorosalicylamide and N-morpholinomethyl 3,5-dichlorosalicylamide have been taken. The former shows bands at 1625 cm.⁻¹, characteristic of -CONH, grouping²², and the latter at 1614 cm.⁻¹ and 1650 cm.⁻¹, characteristic²³ of a monosubstituted amide function, supporting the view that these Mannich bases are carboxamido derivatives.

Like salicylamide¹, it has been possible for us to prepare the N-methylol of 3,5-dibromosalicylamide, which condenses with secondary amines to yield their corresponding N-Mannich bases. This points to the reaction mechanism encountered by Zinner *et al* in benzoxazolone²⁴, benzimidazolone²⁴, Winterfeld and Singh in 2-aza-3-oxoindolizidine²⁵ and Runti in indole²⁶ Mannich bases.

17. Hellmann, H. and Oplitz, G. *«-Aminoalkylierung*, Verlag Chemie, Weinheim, 1960, 13.

18. Reichert, B. *Die Mannich-Reaktion*, Springer Verlag, Berlin, 1959, 53.

19. *cf.* 17, p.64.

20. *Beilstein*, 10, 109.

21. By the courtesy of the Giba Research Centre, Bombay.

22. Bellamy, L. J., "The Infra-red Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen & Co., London, 1962, 203.

23. Zinner *et al.*, *Chem. Ber.*, 1957, 90, 1548.

24. Zinner *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1958, 91, 1482.

25. Winterfeld and Singh, *Arch. Pharmac.*, 1961, 294, 404.

26. Runti, *Gazz. chim. ital.*, 1951, 81, 613.

On the other hand, we could also prepare N-Mannich bases of salicylamide and 3,5-dibromosalicylamide successfully by condensing them with N-methylol piperidine²⁷. The yield however, increases with the addition of HCl (pH ca.5): This corroborates the reaction mechanism of Hellmann *et al.*²⁸.

It may be inferred from the above reaction mechanisms that the reaction follows the third order of kinetics, as studied by Cummings and Shelton²⁹.

The other postulate of Feldmann and Wagner³⁰, that methene-bis-amine³¹, $R_1=N-CH_2-N=R_2$, is also an intermediate in Mannich Condensation, did not succeed in the case of salicylamide/3,5-dibromosalicylamide/3, 5-dichlorosalicylamide.

In conclusion it may be added that these are reversible equilibrium reactions, which could be catalysed by a proton or even a proton extractor, depending upon the nucleophile/electrophile potential of the reaction partners.

Preliminary pharmacological screening show some promise and would be reported in the appropriate columns.

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29. Cummings and Shelton, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 419.
30. Feldmann and Wagner *ibid.*, 1942, **7**, 31.
31. Knövenagel, E., *Chem. Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 2385.